

The Toning with Etching Technique in the Art of Ex-libris

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Abstract

Ex-libris printmaking technique, which is used as a property indicator for private books and in the library system in the historical flow, has become an important branch of art over time and has started to be used in gift giving and artistic fields. Thanks to artistic activities such as international competitions and biennials, the art of Ex-libris has also created a cultural bridge over the world in the last quarter century.

The art of ex-libris means ownership and also makes a kind of promotion of the person or institution on whose behalf it is made. Thus, both ownership and promotional features can be together. In addition to the classical techniques in ex-libris production, new techniques are also used today in accordance with modern technology. Today, computer design applications have been added to high printing techniques such as wood and linoleum and intaglio printing techniques such as copper and zinc. The most widely used technique in the development process has generally been the acid etching technique and its versions.

In this study, first the ex-libris technique will be explained, then the history of the ex-libris art will be briefly mentioned. Then, the acid engraving method will be mentioned and the gradual acid engraving method will be explained by supporting the technical details in the tables. Afterwards, images of 6 ex-libris works will be given and the contribution of the different tones obtained by acid engraving on these works to the painting will be mentioned.

Keywords: Ex-libris, Acid Engraving, C3, Toning, Engraving, Printmaking.

1. About Ex-libris

“Ex-libris are small-sized original works with names and pictures of different subjects on the inner cover of their books by the book lovers. It is the business card or deed of the book. The book introduces the owner, glorifies him, and warns the borrower to return the book. “ (Pektaş, 2017, p. 11) “As a word, it means” from the library of.... “Or” belongs to the library of.... “ (Pektaş, 2017, p.11)

Its past is based on Egypt, Assyria and China in ancient times, although property-containing shapes are similar to ex-libris paintings, we see the first examples in German art in the 15th century, as they are used today. The printing press reproduction system invented by Gutenberg accelerated the printing of books especially in Germany and increased the number of them. With the increase in the number of books, the art of ex-libris began to develop as a property title.

The acceleration of book printing and the increase in the number of prints have also led to an increase in the types of printmaking in general. In order to raise pictures for the rapidly growing books, pictures were carved into wood and reproduction patterns were started to be made. In this process, led by Albert Dürer, engraving masters quickly trained in Germany and many engravings began to be made. Ex-libris art was also affected by this situation.

The pictures that needed to be produced on the book pages, which the printing house reproduced rapidly, were met by the masters who made wooden molds. In a short time, they were joined by masters working with plates made of copper mine. Ex-libris techniques were developing at the same rate as the development of engraving painting techniques. The production of ex-libris was increasing day by day as a sign of ownership for increasing books, and even a book without an ex-libris was called a stepchild.

Picture 1: Ex-libris made for Hans Igler in 1450. C3 (Acid Etching), 190x140 mm. (Pektaş, 2017, p.15).

Etching in the art of engraving and the acid carving technique called C3 in the art of Ex-libris can be found in Germany in the 15th century. In some sources, it is written that Dürer carved with acid in recent years. In the following centuries, ex-libris began to be made in the type of coat of arms. Because before the ex-libris was used in a pictorial sense, carved and embossed crests were made on tools such as armor, shields, swords and spears used in the military field in Europe to represent the owner. Thanks to this habit, the art of ex-libris produced works resembling a coat of arms for a long time.

Picture 2: Rembrandt Harmenszoon van Rijn, “Jesus Shown in Public”, 1655, Acid Engraving and Dry Point. (Küçüköner, 2012, p.30)

Ex-libris, from the emergence of XVII. Until the first half of the 19th century, it contained more coats of arms. From the Middle Ages, weapons, armor and shields had distinctive markings that allowed the cavalry in which it was hidden to be recognized even from afar. These weapons and materials were accepted among the cultured people of the library as a sign of ownership or as a pennant that more quickly introduced the owner of the book. There was no need for an inscription to indicate the person’s name. This could be attributed to the reason why there was a preference for arm-themed Ex-libris at that time (Pektaş, 2017, p.17,18).

Although lines were obtained with acid in engravings and ex-libris, generally single-stage etching was performed, and gradations were obtained only with the frequency and sparseness of the scanning. For the first time, at the beginning of the 17th century, the famous Dutch painter Rembrandt began to achieve tones with acid on the copper plate.

Rembrandt, who was the first artist to use the progressive acid etching method, used line scans and frequencies during drawing for the light-dark balance of the pattern in his early engravings. Over time, he discovered how to acidify the plate with the lines drawn on the wax varnish many times. Instead of forcibly scraping the copper plate with burine, the artist covered it with wax, moistened it and thickened it. After drawing the pattern on the surface with pointed tools, he threw the plate into acid. The scraped areas on the candle were eroded by the acid (Küçüköner, 2012, p.29).

Rembrandt was making interventions on the mold with acid at different stages, reducing the excess lines by crushing, and keeping the lines that should be darker in acid for longer. At the end of these experiences, it was well understood that the waiting of the mold more or less in the acid caused the formation of thin and thick lines in the picture. Instead of forcing it by hand, linear values could be reached easily thanks to acid engraving. These applications have been used among engraving and ex-libris artists, and in time it has been called the gradual etching technique.

Innovations such as the increase in collectors and artistic institutions in the 19th and 20th centuries, the development of modern experimental techniques, and the use of technology in art also affected the art of ex-libris. Today, the art of ex-libris forms an international art network. On behalf of ex-libris, associations, foundations, etc. organizations contribute to the development of this art in different countries.

“20. At the beginning of the century, artists from different disciplines

started to make ex-libris and produced works in their own styles. In this century, ex-libris associations and foundations were established, congresses, exchanges and competitions were started, especially in Europe, and ex-libris museums started to be opened together with collecting.” (Küçüköner, 2020, p.201).

2. Etching (C3) Technique

One of the most frequently used techniques in the art of engraving and ex-libris is the etching technique. This technique, which is called etching in the world, is coded as C3 in the Ex-libris literature. The etching technique includes all kinds of intaglio prints that have already been treated with acid. However, in this study, we will try to define the acid toning technique in particular.

In the acid engraving technique, the artist first creates the design of the work to be done. Prepares the metal sheet of the appropriate size for the mold of the work (the most commonly used sheets today are zinc sheets). Cleans and straightens the surface and sides of the sheet. The top of the board is covered with acid-resistant varnish as a thin surface (today, chassis paint thinned with synthetic thinner is used as varnish). (Table 1).

Table 1. Above is the lateral cross-section of the zinc plate whose sides and surface were cleaned. Below is a side section of the same lacquered plate.

When the varnished surface dries, the artist transfers his previously prepared design to the surface with different methods. One of these methods is the transfer method with carbon paper. The artist places the carbon paper on the lacquered surface and fixes the paper with the previously prepared design on the carbon paper. He draws the design again by pressing it with a pencil, and in the meantime, thanks to the carbon paper, the lines are transferred to the varnished surface. In this transfer, yellow carbon paper can be preferred to make the lines visible on the black lacquer.

After the sketch is transferred to the surface, the drawing process begins. Steel-tipped pens are used for drawing, the contours and interior detail scans of the work are drawn on the varnished surface with steel-tipped

pens. In the dry excavation technique, a hollow line is obtained by groping by pressing the steel tip, while in the acid engraving technique, the steel-tipped pencils are not pressed, but only passed over the varnished surface, thus removing the lacquer from the place where it was passed (Table 2). In the lines where the varnish is removed, the metal surface of the plate is exposed and when the plate is thrown into the acid pool, the acid that comes into contact with the zinc from these open areas begins to pit the plate.

Table 2. Side section of the paths made on the lacquer by scanning with steel tips on the varnished surface of the plate.

Pickling is generally done in 7 stages to create richness of tone. The first of these phases starts at 30 seconds. In a tub filled with nitric acid diluted at a ratio of 1/8, 7 stages of acidification are carried out, while the time scale calculated with the golden ratio is used. In this table, the two previous periods and the previous period are added together to arrive at the new time calculation. Since the places that remain open until the last stage will be exposed to acid every time, the last stage coincides with the deepest stage. (Table 3).

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Phases	Stage Time	Total of Stages	The Overall Total
1. stage	30 sec	30 saniye	
2. stage	30+30 sec	1 minute	1.30 minutes
3. stage	30 sec+1 min	1.30 minutes	3 minutes
4. stage	1 min+1.30 mins	2.30 minutes	5.30 minutes
5. stage	1.30 min+2.30 min	4 minutes	9.30 minutes
6. stage	2. 30 mins+4 mins	6.30 minutes	16 minutes
7. stage	4 mins+6.30 mins	10.30 minutes	26.30 minutes

Table 3. The table showing the times in the 7-stage chart according to the Golden Ratio.

In order to reduce the line thickness in the first stage of the pickling process, the lightest line depths in the picture are obtained by keeping the plate in the acid tub for 30 seconds while all lines are open (Table 4, 1st stage level). When the first stage has expired, the plate is removed from the tub and run through water so that the acid on it does not continue to collapse the plate. The water on its surface is dried with newspaper and dryer. The artist covers these first-level lines on the plate with varnish with thin-nosed brushes. When the varnish dries, the plate is thrown back into the acid cuvette for the second step. This step lasts for 1 minute and the plate is removed from the cuvette and dried (Table 4, 2nd stage level).

Thus, the depth of the second light-toned lines in the picture is reached. The artist also closes these lines with lacquer and prevents further deepening by the acid in the next stages. The artist applies the 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th and 7th stages, respectively, in this way. In the last 7th stage, the darkest line level is reached by keeping the plate in the acid cuvette for 10.5 minutes (Table 4, 7th stage level). The lines that came without being closed until this last stage were exposed to acid at every stage. When we add all the times on top of each other, the lines in this last stage, which remained in the acid for 26.30 minutes, were the deepest lines of the plate.

Table 4. The table showing that the exposed lines on the varnished surface were precipitated by the acid and the time and depth differences in 7-stage etching.

While in the acid tub, we see that the acidic water bubbles from the scratched areas. These bubbles, which are produced by the acid as the metal melts the metal as a result of a chemical reaction and turns it into water, are brought to the water surface by shaking the tub from time to time. In addition, the fact that the bubbles are few and slow indicates that the strength of the acid is weakened, and the fact that the bubbles are many and fast indicates that the strength of the acid is too high.

After the pickling process is finished, we take the board out of the acid tub and clean the surface of the board by wiping the varnish layers on it with synthetic thinner. When the varnish layer on the plate is cleaned, we can see our lines and scans structured at seven different depths (Table 5). At this stage, the sheet becomes the mold of our work. The pattern of our work has been formed and it has become ready to print by dyeing.

Table 5. Table showing the time and depth differences in the seven-stage etched plate.

The first paint is given to the mold and the paint on the surface is cleaned with the field or newspaper. Only the deep lines created by the acid are left behind. Different densities have occurred at each depth, and these different densities will be transferred to the engraving paper during printing.

After the paint on the surface is cleaned, our mold is placed on the press table. Our engraving paper, which was previously kept in the water tub, is removed from the tub and the water on its surface is removed with thin papers. Thanks to this wetting, the engraving paper's fibers are swollen and ready for printing. The moist paper is placed on the mold on the tray.

The felt in the press is also covered on them, and in this state, the handle of the press is turned and the plate and the mold on it and the engraving paper are passed under the tight cylinder. With the support of the felt, the engraving paper is embedded in the lines on the mold and absorbs the paint in the line slots. Thanks to the printing, the picture in the mold is transferred onto the engraving paper. Line clusters of 7 different thicknesses in the pattern also appear on paper. When viewed from the side section, 7 different line tones from thin to thick can be seen on the paper (Table 6).

30 seconds	1 minute	1.5 minute	2.5 minute	4 minute	6.5 minute	10.5 minute
1 stage	2 stage	3 stage	4 stage	5 stage	6 stage	7 stage
Total:	Total:	Total:	Total:	Total:	Total:	Total:
30 sc.	1.5 min.	3 min.	5.5 min.	9.5 min.	16 min.	26.5 min.

Table 6. Table showing the paint thicknesses transferred from the 7-stage mold to the paper in the acid etching- C3 technique.

When the printed paper is looked at carefully from the top, the line thicknesses between the first stage and the last stage can be noticed. Stage 1 has the thinnest lines. The lines in the 2nd stage are slightly thicker than the previous one. The lines in each next step are thicker than the previous lines. The lines in the 7th stage are the thickest lines. Since the line channel in the first stage is of very weak depth, a very slight amount of paint clings to it, and this paint passes on to the paper as the thinnest line with the press. The line channel in the last stage is the deepest channel on the mold and it happens when the paint piled up in this channel is both spread on both sides and fluffy due to the density as it passes onto the paper during the pressing process. (Table 7).

Table 7. The table showing the line thicknesses passing from the 7-stage mold to the paper in the acid etching- C3 technique.

Baskı yapılan kağıda üstten dikkatlice bakıldığında ise ilk aşama ile son aşama arasındaki çizgi kalınlıklarının fark edilebilmektedir. 1. aşamadaki en ince çizgiler yer alır. 2. aşamadaki çizgiler bir öncekinden az daha kalındırlar. Her sonraki aşamadaki çizgiler bir önceki çizgilerden kalındır. 7. aşamadaki çizgiler ise en kalın olan çizgilerdir. İlk aşamadaki çizgi kanalı çok zayıf derinlikte olduğu için içerisinde çok hafif miktarda boya

Picture 3: Peter Ford, 2001, Ex libris Michael Zirinsky, C3,C5, 65x93 mm.(1st International Ex-libris Competition Exhibition Catalogue, 2003, p. 57)

tutunmakta ve bu boya da pres ile beraber kağıda en ince çizgi olarak geçmektedir. En son aşamadaki çizgi kanalı kalıp üzerindeki en derin kanaldır ve bu kanala yığılan boyanın pres sürecinde kağıda geçerken yoğunluktan dolayı hem iki tarafa yayılması, hem de kabarık olması ile olur. (Tablo 7).

3. Examples of Work Made Using Acid Engraving-Etching- C3 Technique in Ex-libris Art

So far, we have talked about the definition of ex-libris art and a brief historical process. Then, we tried to convey information about this technique by talking about the definition and historical development of engraving and acid etching- C3 technique. We tried to explain the 7-stage toning method used in the acid engraving method and the formation of tonal differences with sample figures. In this section, we will include examples of ex-libris artifacts made using these techniques. We will try to evaluate the ex-libris works in the images in terms of technical and intonation formation.

Picture 3 shows an ex-libris made in 2001 by artist Peter Ford, born in 1937 in England. Although both C3 (acid engraving) and C5 (aquatinta) techniques were used in the study, the acid engraving technique shows itself more in the painting. After transferring his design to the plate, the artist left the writings on the bottom and the backs of the writing pens in the picture without scratching them with scraping tips, leaving them varnished. Thus, since these varnished areas were never precipitated by the acid in the acid tub, they did not deepen and remained on the surface and remained white by not holding paint during printing.

After the white areas were covered, the plate was acidified. All open channels were precipitated for 30 seconds in the first step in acid. When this period is over, the plate is removed from the acid tub and the areas that are desired to remain in the lightest shade are covered with varnish. These regions are areas of light gray value that occupy a large area in the background of the picture. These newly lacquered areas continued to deepen in the acid tub on the areas that were initially covered with vefnik to keep them white. At this stage, the plate is kept in the acid tub for about 1 minute. These gray areas, which are a darker shade of the lightest gray tone, are placed next to the lightest shade in the picture.

In the third stage, the necessary places on the plate were covered with varnish again for a dark tone. At this stage, the plate, which was kept in the acid tub for 1.5 minutes, was removed and the artist covered it with some

Picture 4: Carla Fusi, 2004, C3, 126x87 mm. (12th International Ex-libris Competition Exhibition Catalogue, 2007, p. 57)

more varnish for the next stage and was thrown into the tub. Continuing in this way, the stages were completed and all the remaining areas on the plate were covered with varnish until the darkest linear areas remained light in the seventh stage. The plate was left in the acid tub for about 10.30 minutes. Thus, since the last remaining linear areas were precipitated on top of each other by the acid, they were subjected to precipitation for about 26.30 minutes in total and became the deepest areas.

The plate was removed from the tub and the varnish was removed. We refer to the state of the plate at this stage as a mold, since many prints can be made from it afterwards. The artist gave the paint on the mold, cleared the paint on the surfaces with tartan, created the white areas, laid the damp paper on the mold and pressed it, and finally obtained the picture seen in visual 3. Since the paint adhered to the thinnest linear channels formed during the minimum time the plate was waiting in the acid tub, the lines in those areas in the picture also formed the thinnest and weakest line areas. Moderately pitted channels in the middle stages formed moderate lines in the printing stage, as they were able to hold medium levels of dye. Linear areas that were exposed to acid the most during the pickling process and that formed the deepest channels were the areas that retained the most paint. During printing, they gave the thickest and densest paint to the paper, creating the thickest and darkest areas in the picture.

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In accordance with the artist's design, we can say that the open spaces seen in the work consist of large areas covered by fine lines in the first stages. The dark areas are seen in the linear structure in the picture and form the contour lines of the writing pens in the picture. The artist kept the ex libris writing in acid until the last stage, allowing it to reach the darkest tone, on the contrary, he covered the name of the person on whose behalf it was made in the first stage and kept it in a white tone.

Thus, a black-white contrast was created in the picture. The white texts interacted with the light areas in the picture, and the dark texts interacted with the dark areas in the picture. In addition, the artist made horizontal scanning of lines in thin and weak linear tone areas that cover large areas in the background. He made the vertical scans used in the tones of the writing pens he placed vertically on the upper plan of the painting and created a balance between the background and the foreground.

In Picture 4, we see an ex-libris work made in 2004 by artist Carla Fusi, who was born in Italy in 1983. In the study, the C3 (acid engraving) technique was used successfully by stepwise acidification, and thanks to the thin-thick differences between the resulting line thicknesses, foreground

and background could be created between the vertical elements (trees) that cover the whole of the picture. The artist first cleaned his plate and obtained the thin layer by applying varnish to its surface. Then she transferred her design to the varnished surface of the plate and completed it by drawing and scanning all the lines and scans in the picture on this surface with the scraping tips.

After the drawing and scanning process was completed, the plate was thrown into acid. In the first step in acid, all open channels were immersed for 30 seconds and precipitated equally. At the end of the period, the plate was removed from the tub and the places that were desired to have a depth of 30 seconds were covered with lacquer. At this stage, the channels formed in the first 30 seconds in an area covered with varnish were also closed, and further deepening was prevented by exposure to acid in the following periods. When we examine the picture closely, we see that at this stage, the tree branches near the right and left edges of the picture, some of the tree branches interspersed in the areas near the top of the picture, and some of the lines in the grassy and bush areas on the forest floor at the bottom are covered. At the stages of creating these and other light tones, the top, bottom and sides of the painting were made in light tones, while the dense tree trunks in the middle were made in medium and dark tones. Thus, both the painting was centered and the circulation of the rays of the sun on the hill in the forest and the luminous values created on hot summer days were obtained.

The artist applied the stages in order. In the second stage, he covered the adjacent lines of the branches on the top, bottom and two sides, which we explained in the first stage with varnish, and enabled us to perceive the branches and structure in the picture more easily by providing the transition of light from the lightest tone to the closest middle tone. The viewer's eye wanders freely on this gradual transitional tonality.

Picture 5: Toni Pecoraro, Ex-libris Marco Fragonara, 1998, C3,C5,C6, 134X132 mm. (Virtual 1)

Applying the third and subsequent stages sequentially, the artist created successive tonal increases in the first stages and made the painting easier to read. The dark-toned scans on the tree trunks in the middle of the picture, where dark tones are dominant, and the white space between the trees cause an ordinary contrast in the picture and ensure that the trees are perceived as in harsh sunlight. With the seventh stage, the lines and scans of the trees in the middle remained in the acid for about 26.30 minutes. Scans in these trees created the deepest channels of the picture.

The varnished area on the surface of the plate has been cleaned and the mold has been prepared for printing. The deepest channels on the die

were the areas that took the most paint and left the most intense and wide paint on the paper. When the artist paints the mold and prints it, he has achieved the result seen in the image. The lines and scans that were closed in the first stages on the plate, which were kept in the acid tub for different periods, formed as thin channels, and as a result, they formed thin and weak lines because they held little paint. Medium depth channels, which are kept and structured in medium periods, created the middle tones in the picture because they hold medium paint. The channels that were kept in acid the most, formed the darkest tones in the picture.

In Picture 5, we see an ex-libris work made in 1998 by the Italian born artist Toni Pecoraro. The artist is known for his labyrinth-themed works in woodcut painting. The artist, who uses printing techniques with a unique style, also has ex-libris works that he blends with acid engraving, aquatinta and sugar varnish technique. Although both C3 (acid engraving), C5 (aquatinta) and C6 (sugar tile) techniques were used together in the ex-libris work in Picture 5, the acid engraving technique showed itself more in the painting.

The picture shows the landscape of the mountains and the city in the background, with a labyrinth deeply embedded in the large expanse between the city and the plain in the foreground. The labyrinth is actually a snake. In the lower part of the picture, on the flat area closest to us in front of the landscape, a cage made of sharpened stakes at both ends, connected by ropes is seen. Inside the cage, there is a male figure holding the stakes.

The artist first created his plate and covered it with varnish, transferring his design to the surface. After the white areas in the picture were closed, the plate was thrown into acid for the first 30 seconds. At the end of the period, the plate was removed from the acid tub and the lightest tone after white was covered with lacquer again by the artist using a brush. The white areas are structured according to the direction of the light, as in classical paintings. Illuminated areas take up a lot of space in the city image, which is in the background in the picture. In the labyrinth, both light and dark are in balance. After the first stage, the necessary places were covered with varnish again in accordance with the design, and the plate was thrown into the acid tub for the next stage.

Picture 6: Ryszard Balon, “Ex-libris Rauf Denktaş”, 2011, C3, (Ex-libris Rauf Raif Denktaş Exhibition Catalogue, 2012, P.16)

Line clusters of different thicknesses were formed by throwing the sheet into the acid cuvette in seven stages. In the painting, where the light tones occupy more space, the darkest tones are used to reveal the shapes of the piles and the shadows of the curves of the snake forming the labyrinth. The lines of the figure inside the cage, which consists of piles formed with the darkest tones, were created with the subtle tones in the first two stages. The artist used the varnish he took on his brush during the etching process

to close the lines of the figure between the piles. In the first two stages, all the lines in the figure were structured, but since the total duration of the stages was short, the depth of these structured lines was also less, and the ink entering these thin channels and the transition to the paper during printing were also thin and weak. The artist was able to transform the progressive acid etching technique to present such a rich tonality into an aesthetic appearance to his work.

In Picture 6, we see an ex-libris work made in 2011 by artist Ryszard Balon, born in 1944 in Poland. In this work, which the artist sent to a competition held for the President of the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus, Rauf Denktaş, in 2011, the C3 (acid engraving) technique was successfully used by stepping into acid. In this painting, Rauf Denktaş is shown as the representative of hope and peace in the mouth of a pigeon against the anxiety and dark days on the island of Cyprus.

The striped areas that are kept in acid for a little while create a suitable fine tone in the picture and especially by making the brown paint become lighter in these areas, it makes it perceived as if there are more than one color in the picture. In addition, light-medium-dark tones are seen in equal amounts to each other.

Similar to what we have explained in other examples, in this work, the artist first covered his plate with varnish and transferred his design to this surface. Then, as a first step, he left the plate in the acid tub and removed it after 30 seconds and covered the line clusters that he wanted to have the thinnest thickness with the help of a brush with varnish. Unlike other examples, in this study, individual lines were not closed, on the contrary, line clusters with more than one line next to each other were closed. After the closure process, the plate was left in the acid bath again and was removed by waiting for 1 minute. At this stage, the artist covered the areas that needed to be closed with varnish and laid the plate back in the acid tub. This process continued in succession and the last step, in which thick lines were formed, was completed and the plate was removed from the acid cuvette.

The artist has made toning for the form in general, and has reached a clear formal structure by preferring different darkneses in the dimensions of the forms instead of making the shadows of the forms dark. While the outward facing columns of the two buildings facing each other, the inward surfaces are structured in the darkest tone, the outer surfaces are structured in the lightest tone and an extreme contrast is achieved. Column shadows falling on the intermediate wall surfaces between the columns are rendered in medium-light tones. Just as the inward sides of the columns are rendered in the darkest shade, the surfaces of the windows inside the building, the interiors of the drawers on the lower floor, and the liquid-like structure that

Picture 7: Fevzi Tüfekçi, "Ex libris Nazım Hikmet 1902-2002", (Ex Libris Nazım Hikmet 1902-2002 Exhibition Catalogue, 2002, P. 72

Picture 8: The state of the work in Picture 7 showing the black and white tone values.

forms the ex libris letter by flowing from the drawers to the floor are also processed in the darkest tone. This extreme darkness creates gloom and restlessness in the picture. The light-toned body of the dove soaring from the sky and the white fabric-like object it carries in its mouth add a positive energy to the work as a representative of hope and peace, despite the gloom at the bottom of the painting.

In Picture 7, we see an ex-libris work made in 2002 using two different molds belonging to Fevzi Tüfekçi, who was born in 1948 in Prizren and has been continuing his art life in Turkey since 1971. The artist used the 7-stage etching (Etching - C3) technique in this work.

The artist made his design according to two patterns. One pattern with cool tints and the majority of the image, and the other with warm tints and little of the image over it. While creating these two molds, he first acidified one and then the other.

The artist first transferred his design to the mold and made drawings and scans where he saw fit. Then, for the first 30-second step, he placed the mold in the acid cuvette, respectively. We can see the tonal value that emerges at this stage in the near-white tone area at the bottom of the rightmost vertical form of the work (Picture 8, no: 1). After the molds were processed, they were removed from the tub and dried. The artist covered the areas that should remain as the lightest shade on the plate with varnish with the help of a brush and prevented the acid from continuing to carve in the subsequent pickling processes. In the second step, the plate was thrown into the acid bath again and removed by waiting for 1 minute at this stage. At the end of this stage, areas in one dark tone of the lightest gray were formed on the plate. The tone value obtained at this stage is seen in Picture 8 in a strip-like shape no. The plate was removed from the acid bath, dried and prepared for lacquering.

When it comes to the third stage, the artist covered those areas with varnish on the plate and laid the plate in an acid tub so that the two-tone values would be constant. Areas number two, which were closed with varnish, were fixed like areas number one, which was closed in the previous step, and the acid was prevented from re-processing in this area. The plate was removed by keeping it in the cuvette for about 1.30 minutes. At the end of this stage, gray areas with a darker tone than the previous tone were formed on the plate. We can see the tonal value formed at this stage in a strip-like shape that bends like a tall ellipse next to the previous tone (Picture 8, no: 3).

When it comes to the fourth stage, as in the other stages, the areas that were acidified in the previous stage and where the formed tone value should remain constant, were covered with varnish. The plate was again

Picture 9: Mustafa Küçüköner, "Ex-Libris Hasip Pektaş", 2005, C3, Diameter: 12cm, (Mustafa Küçüköner Collection)

thrown into the acid cuvette and removed after 2.30 minutes. In this stage, as in the others, deepening was provided to create a dark gray area on the plate that is darker than the previous tone. We can see the tonal value formed at this stage in the 4th area of picture 8 and in other areas as it occupies a large area.

In the fifth, sixth and seventh stages, as in the previous stages, the places where the acidified depth should be kept constant were closed. Then, the pickling process was carried out in accordance with the times specified in Table 3. It was kept in acid for 4 minutes in the fifth stage, 6.30 minutes in the sixth stage and 10.30 minutes in the seventh stage. When it comes out of the acid, the depth that will give a darker tone than the previous tone on the plate at each stage and the depth that will give the darkest tone in the seventh stage has been reached.

In Picture 8, we can see the tonal values of the fifth, sixth and seventh stages, as in the other stages. When we examine it sequentially, we see the tonal value formed in the fifth stage in the area 5 and in the surrounding areas, as on the large vertical form in the middle area in the picture. We can see the tonal value formed in the sixth stage in the area 6 and in the surrounding areas, as on the large vertical form on the left in the picture. We can see the tone value formed in the seventh stage in the picture above and in the area 7, as on the large horizontal region forming the background.

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Similar processes were carried out on the other plate that gave warm tone values, and the color of the two molds was given to the press, and the result seen in color in picture 7 was obtained. The cool tone plate and the warm color tone plate are combined on gravure paper during printing. When the 7 different tone values that exist in them come together, different new tones are formed and this mixture has turned into an extra aesthetic value in painting.

In Picture 9, we see the Turkish artist Mustafa Küçüköner's work called "Ex-Libris Hasip Pektaş" made in 2005. In this study, the 7-stage etching system of the etching-C3) technique was used. The tonal differences in the work are easily seen in the detail image in Picture 10. In addition, in the study, similar to the study in picture 7, it was created by cross hatching. Thanks to both the sparse and tightness of the scanning and the 7-stage acidification, a very rich tonality has been achieved in the picture.

Picture 10: Section from Picture 9. The state showing the Black - White Tone Values.

The artist first transferred the design he had prepared on the plate, which he had covered with a thin layer of varnish, and made lines and scans on the surface with scraping tips. When viewed in this state, all lines on the surface are seen in the same thickness and tone. However, the lines on the plate, which are kept in acid for 7 stages, will reach different depths and will turn into lines of different thicknesses in the appearance of the print on

the paper.

After all the drawings on the plate were finished, the plate was thrown into the acid tub for 30 seconds for the first step, and then it was removed and the surface was dried. The places with the number 1 tone value in the section shown in Picture 10 were covered with varnish and placed in the acid tub again. In the second stage, the plate was kept in the tub for 1 minute and was again removed and dried. This time, the places with the 2nd tone value were covered with varnish and the third stage was started. In the third step, the plate was kept in the cuvette for 1.5 minutes, removed from the cuvette and dried. This process was applied successively for the other stages as well.

When it comes to the seventh stage, the lines of all tonal values, except the lines that will create the darkest tone on the plate surface, are seen to be completely covered with varnish. Only the areas that were desired to be deepened in the last stage were left uncovered. At this final stage, the plate was removed by keeping it in the acid cuvette for 10.5 minutes and dried. Since acidification will not be done again, the varnish layer on the plate was cleaned with synthetic thinner.

Now the pattern of the work is ready and the number of artists has taken the prints from the pattern in the amount and color that he has determined. Thanks to the seven-stage etching, areas of seven different tones were formed in the picture, and this difference in tonality gave the painting an aesthetic value.

Result

In this article, which we have discussed under the title of “Toning with Acid Engraving Technique (C3) in Ex-libris Art”, the art of ex-libris has been described, and the history of engraving and ex-libris arts has been briefly looked at. The technique known as ‘etching’ in the art of engraving and ‘C3’ in the art of ex-libris has been explained, and the technical details of gradual acid engraving are explained in 7 tables. In the light of these technical details, 6 ex-libris works were evaluated one by one, and the tonal differences obtained by gradual pickling processes were tried to be shown on the ex-libris samples given in the visuals.

As a result, it has been seen that 7 different tones can be obtained with the gradual pickling method in the art of Ex-libris. In classical works, the artist achieved light and dark tones with sparse or tight line scans on the plate. In progressive acid etching, the artist’s options for creating tones have increased. Today, the artist can produce works with rich tonal power by obtaining lines in different tonality through 7-stage pickling.

The technique and application forms in the 7-stage pickling method have been tried to be explained in detail in this article and a resource has been created for the artist candidates who want to make ex-libris work with the staged engraving method.

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Table Sources

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Table 4. Source: Mustafa Küçüköner

Table 5. Source: Mustafa Küçüköner

Table 6. Source: Mustafa Küçüköner

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Picture Sources

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Picture 3. I. International Ex-libris Competition Exhibition Catalogue, (2003), Hacettepe University, Ankara Ex-libris Association, Ankara, 57.

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Picture 5. Virtual 1. https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Toni_Pecoraro_Ex-libris_Marco_Fragonara.jpg

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Picture 7. Ex Libris Nazım Hikmet 1902-2002, (2002). Istanbul Ex Libris Academy Association Publications, Istanbul, P. 72.

Picture 8. The state of the work in Picture 7 showing the black and white tone values

Picture 9. Mustafa Küçüköner Collection.

Picture 10. Section from Picture 9. The state showing the Black - White Tone Values.